

How Blackholes project information from the bulk to the boundary (holographic screen).

Quantum Information Holography (QIH) Framework:

Quantum State Representation in Hilbert Space:

Let H represent the Hilbert space of the Boundary, with quantum states $|\psi\rangle$ spanning the manifold M . $|\psi\rangle = \int_M \psi(x) |x\rangle dx$

Hamiltonian Representation:

Express the Hawking radiation as the Hamiltonian $H^\wedge$ with eigenstates $|\psi\rangle$. $H^\wedge |\psi\rangle = h |\psi\rangle$

Observation Framework:

Projection Operator for Singularity:

The operator $P^\wedge$ projects the unobservable singularity, C , onto the observable space of the Boundary, H . $P^\wedge: C \rightarrow H$ $P^\wedge |\chi\rangle = |\psi\rangle$

Qubits and Quantum Information:

Representation of Qubit States:

Denote qubit states $|q\rangle$ within the subspace Q of H , with the Hawking operator $H^\wedge$ applied. $\langle q | H^\wedge | q \rangle = h$

Interaction of Quantum States:

Interference Operator:

The interference operator $I^\wedge$ with $|p\rangle$ and $|np\rangle$ denoting states in prime and non-prime regions respectively. $I^\wedge |p\rangle = |p|p\rangle$ $I^\wedge |np\rangle = |np|np\rangle$

Understanding the Overall Projection:

Complete Operator for Projection:

The total projection operator $O^\wedge$ as a composition of $P^\wedge$, $H^\wedge$, and $I^\wedge$. $O^\wedge = P^\wedge \circ H^\wedge \circ I^\wedge$ Achieve the projection onto the holographic screen from the singularity state $|\chi\rangle$. $O^\wedge|\chi\rangle = |\phi\rangle$

This framework underscores the interplay of quantum states, Hamiltonian dynamics, and projection operations within the boundary and bulk in the QIH context, providing a comprehensive perspective on the quantum informational and holographic principles in the analysis of cosmic phenomena.

Overview:

In the QIH framework, we explore the cosmos's unique elements: the Boundary (a conceptual outer layer) and the Bulk (the inner universe). Think of the boundary as the edge of a spinning disk and the bulk as everything inside it.

Quantum States and Space:

- **Hilbert Space:** Within the boundary, imagine a multidimensional space called Hilbert Space where all possible quantum states live. Each state is like a point in this space, and its position and properties are detailed mathematically.
- **Hamiltonian Dynamics:** The Hamiltonian, which we articulate as Hawking radiation in this framework, helps understand how these states evolve over time. It's like the rules of motion for the quantum states within the boundary.

Observational Context:

- **Projection Operator:** The unobservable aspects within the bulk (or singularity) are mapped onto the observable boundary. This mapping allows us to study and understand the otherwise inaccessible aspects of the singularity.

Quantum Information:

- **Qubits:** Qubits (quantum bits) are the basic units of quantum information within the Hilbert Space. They interact according to the rules set by the Hamiltonian, and this interaction is consistent and measurable, ensuring the stability of quantum information processing.

Interaction of Quantum States:

- **Interference Operator:** Different quantum states within the boundary (prime and non-prime states) interact with each other, creating interference patterns. This interaction

plays a crucial role in understanding the structure and behavior of quantum states in the boundary.

Projection of the Bulk onto the Boundary:

- **Overall Projection:** *Finally, all the information and interactions within the bulk are projected onto the boundary. This projection allows us to "see" and "understand" the happenings within the bulk by studying the boundary.*

Conclusion:

In essence, the QIH framework provides a way to study and understand the unobservable aspects of the universe (bulk and singularity) by observing and analyzing the boundary. It interweaves quantum states, Hamiltonian dynamics, and quantum information to offer insights into the cosmos's intricate structure and behavior.